

Toward an Operational Intrusion Detection and Prevention System for SDN-IoT: A Cascaded Deep Learning Approach with Automatic Mitigation

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Abstract—The convergence of software-defined networking and the Internet of Things widens the attack surface of connected networks and calls for defenses able to detect attacks at the controller's vantage point and to block them there. Earlier work compared deep architectures for denial-of-service attack detection and opened two perspectives: extension to the multiclass setting and integration into an operational intrusion detection and prevention system acting in real time. This article takes up these perspectives in an SDN-IoT context. On ASEADOS-SDN-IoT, a recent dataset that synchronizes device traffic with controller telemetry, we evaluate a deep detector organized as a two-stage cascade covering five traffic classes, comparing six architectures at each stage. The hybrid CNN-BiLSTM network offers the best trade-off, and the cascade outperforms a direct multiclass classifier evaluated under identical conditions. We then integrate this detector into a Ryu controller: the sixty-three features are reconstructed online, the cascade decides at every cycle, and a targeted OpenFlow mitigation blocks the attack source after hysteresis confirmation. A functional demonstration on four attack scenarios and a deployability analysis of the full online feature set complete the study. The results delineate both the scope and the limits of the system.

Keywords—Cybersecurity; deep learning; intrusion detection and prevention system (IDPS); software-defined networking (SDN); Internet of Things (IoT); mitigation; cascaded classification; ASEADOS-SDN-IoT.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) connects a growing number of heterogeneous and often resource-constrained devices, from home sensors to industrial controllers. This proliferation widens the attack surface accordingly: connected objects, poorly equipped with defense mechanisms and rarely updated, have become prime targets and relays for large-scale attacks [1], [2], [3]. Distributed denials of service, reconnaissance scans and botnets are among the most frequent threats in these environments [4], [5].

Software-defined networking (SDN) changes the way these networks are monitored. By separating the control plane from the data plane and centralizing decisions in a programmable controller, it offers a global view of traffic and a single point of action to apply countermeasures [6], [7]. This architecture is doubly attractive for IoT security: the controller exposes flow statistics that a detector can exploit, and it can install filtering rules directly. In return, centralization introduces its own risks, the controller becoming a sensitive target [6].

Signature-based classical intrusion detection systems (IDS) struggle to keep pace with the rapid evolution of threats and remain blind to novel attacks [8], [9]. Deep learning offers an alternative: applied to network flows, it learns discriminative representations without explicit rules and detects anomalous behaviors that signatures miss [10], [11]. Many studies have confirmed the value of convolutional, recurrent and hybrid

networks for intrusion detection on IoT traffic [12], [13], [14], [15], including within SDN architectures [16], [17], [18].

This study directly extends two earlier works devoted to comparing deep architectures for denial-of-service attack detection in enterprise networks [19], [20]. The first establishes binary detection, the second extends it to attack-family classification; both designate CNN-BiLSTM as the best model. Above all, they explicitly state the perspectives that remain open: integrating the model into an operational intrusion detection and prevention system (IDPS) able to detect attacks and to block them automatically in real time, and evaluating it on real network flows under operational conditions [19]. We take up these perspectives and carry them into an SDN-IoT context, where the controller provides both the vantage point and the means of action.

Concretely, we evaluate a deep cascaded detector on ASEADOS-SDN-IoT [21], a recent dataset that synchronizes device traffic with controller telemetry and covers five classes (legitimate, DoS, DDoS, botnet, reconnaissance), then integrate it into a Ryu controller with automatic mitigation. The contributions are as follows:

- A cascaded intrusion detector for SDN-IoT covering the five classes of ASEADOS-SDN-IoT, comparing six deep architectures (MLP, LSTM, GRU, CNN, CNN-LSTM, CNN-BiLSTM) at each stage; CNN-BiLSTM offers the best trade-off.
- A controlled comparison between the cascade and a direct multiclass classifier, under identical conditions and on the

same test set, establishing a modest but consistent gain in favor of the cascade.

- Integration of the detector into an operational IDPS: deployment in a Ryu controller, online reconstruction of the sixty-three features by a FlowTracker, and cascaded inference at each supervision cycle.
- An automatic, targeted mitigation: installation of an OpenFlow drop rule on the source-victim pair after hysteresis confirmation, with a blocking duration that depends on the attack family, realizing the IDPS perspective of [19], [20].
- A deployability analysis: the cost, for the SDN control plane, of computing the full feature set online, established as an operational result.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. Section II situates the work in the literature. Section III describes the data, the architectures, the cascade, then the SDN integration and the mitigation. Section IV presents the detection results, the functional demonstration of the IDPS, the deployability analysis and the discussion. Section V concludes.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Deep Learning for Intrusion Detection in the IoT

The application of deep learning to IoT security has been the subject of several recent surveys, which catalog its architectures, datasets and open challenges [1], [2], [8], [10], [11], [22]. These reviews converge on two observations: deep models often outperform signature-based approaches on network traffic, but their evaluation remains fragmented for lack of representative datasets and homogeneous comparisons [23], [9], [24]. On the empirical side, convolutional, recurrent and hybrid networks have been applied to attack detection on IoT flows with good results [12], [13], [25], [26], [14], [15]. Most, however, focus on a single architecture and a binary decision, without systematically comparing several model families under a common protocol.

B. Deep-Learning Intrusion Detection in SDN-IoT Networks

By centralizing network decisions and exposing flow statistics to the controller, SDN provides a natural vantage point for a learned detector [6], [7]. Several works exploit this property. Chaganti et al. propose an IDS based on an LSTM network for multiclass attack classification in SDN-driven IoT networks, evaluated on two SDN-IoT-oriented datasets [18]. Javeed et al. describe a hybrid deep framework combining gated recurrent units and a bidirectional LSTM, trained on a general-purpose corpus (CICIDS2018) with very high accuracy [17]. Other approaches favor lightness: the SDN-IoT IDS of [16] delegates detection to the controller so as not to burden constrained objects, while Maray et al. combine metaheuristic feature selection and a convolutional autoencoder [27]. There are also frameworks integrating SDN, deep learning and distributed ledgers [28], intelligent IoT-oriented IDS [29], [30], automatic

detection systems for SDN and IoT [31], and reinforcement-learning approaches jointly targeting security and performance [32]. The explainability of decisions has also been addressed in this context [33].

Two limitations run through these works. On the one hand, many rely on corpora that do not capture the dynamics specific to the SDN control plane (generic network-security datasets), which restricts the reach of conclusions in the SDN-IoT context. On the other hand, evaluation is often limited to a single model or a binary decision, without a controlled comparison between direct classification and a staged organization.

C. Detection and Mitigation of Denial-of-Service Attacks

Denial of service, in its distributed forms, concentrates a large share of SDN-IoT work, extending to effective mitigation of flows. Machine-learning-based frameworks have been proposed to detect DDoS attacks in software-defined IoT [34], sometimes coupled with an adaptive response [35] or a one-versus-rest strategy for the connected home [36]. Several recent reviews survey these detection and mitigation strategies [4], [5], [37], [38]. These contributions mostly target a single threat; the simultaneous recognition of several attack families, and the associated mitigation, is less addressed.

D. Datasets for SDN-IoT

The choice of dataset conditions the validity of an SDN-IoT IDS. InSDN [39] constituted a first intrusion dataset dedicated to SDN, but without an IoT focus. ASEADOS-SDN-IoT [21], which we use, fills this gap: built on a controller-driven OpenFlow testbed mixing physical and virtual objects, it synchronizes packet flow data with controller telemetry under benign and adversarial conditions. It comprises 457,044 labeled flows described by 83 statistical attributes and covers four attack families (DoS, DDoS, Probe, Botnet) in addition to legitimate traffic. Its cross-layer visibility makes it a suitable basis for evaluating a detector learned at the controller's vantage point.

E. Positioning

Our work follows the methodological line of the deep-architecture comparisons for DDoS detection conducted by OUATTARA et al. [19], [20], [40], who evaluate several models, including CNN-BiLSTM, for binary and multiclass DDoS detection on CIC-DDoS2019. We transpose and extend this approach to the SDN-IoT context in three respects. First, the evaluation is on the dedicated ASEADOS-SDN-IoT dataset [21] and its five classes, rather than a general-purpose DDoS corpus. Second, we compare six architectures (MLP, LSTM, GRU, CNN, CNN-LSTM, CNN-BiLSTM) under a common protocol, at each stage. Third, we explicitly contrast a cascade-organized detection (binary then multiclass) with a direct multiclass classification, under strictly identical conditions, to measure the real contribution of the split rather than postulate it. This controlled comparison, on a recent SDN-IoT dataset and at the

controller's vantage point, distinguishes our contribution from the works recalled above. We further extend these works toward prevention: where [19], [20] stop at detection and call for a real-time IDPS, we integrate the detector into a Ryu controller endowed with automatic mitigation.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset and Features

We evaluate the system on ASEADOS-SDN-IoT [21], a recent dataset dedicated to intrusion detection in SDN-IoT environments. Unlike general-purpose network-security corpora, ASEADOS was built in a topology driven by an SDN controller: it associates connected-object traffic with the flow statistics observable on the controller side, which corresponds precisely to our detector's vantage point. The raw dataset contains 457,044 labeled network flows. Each flow belongs to one of the five retained classes: legitimate traffic (Benign) and four attack families, denial of service (Dos), distributed denial of service (DDoS), botnet traffic (Bot) and reconnaissance scanning (Prob).

The published dataset describes each flow with 83 attributes. We adopt the subset of sixty-three features retained by the dataset authors [21]: from the initial 83 attributes, 63 are kept after removing identification fields and attributes with near-zero variance or strong collinearity, which add no discriminative power and harm generalization. We therefore work in the same feature space as the references published on this dataset. The 63 remaining features describe flow dynamics: duration, byte and packet counts per direction, packet-length statistics, inter-arrival times (IAT), TCP flags, throughputs, subflows and active/idle phases. The ordered list is fixed once and for all, since the same order is replayed at inference time on the controller side.

The class distribution is strongly imbalanced: legitimate traffic and denials of service dominate, while the Bot and Prob classes remain in the minority (Fig. 1). This imbalance drives several preprocessing and training choices described below, as well as the chosen evaluation criterion.

Fig. 1. Distribution of the five traffic classes in ASEADOS-SDN-IoT (marked imbalance of the Bot and Prob classes).

B. Preprocessing

Preprocessing follows a single chain applied identically to all compared configurations, and largely reuses the protocol of the reference works [19], [20]: standardization by centering and scaling estimated on the training set, numeric label encoding and a stratified 60/15/25 split. We first select the 63 features, then remove the infinite and missing values produced by some throughput computations on very short flows; this step brings the dataset to 427,042 usable flows. To limit the effect of extreme values, frequent under flooding attacks, without losing samples, we clip each feature to its 0.5% and 99.5% quantiles rather than removing the flows concerned.

Labels are encoded numerically (Benign = 0, Dos = 1, DDoS = 2, Bot = 3, Prob = 4). The dataset is then split in a stratified manner into training, validation and test at a 60/15/25 ratio, with a random seed fixed at 42 for reproducibility; stratification preserves the proportion of the five classes in each subset. The resulting test set comprises 106,761 flows (58,437 Benign, 31,627 Dos, 12,567 DDoS, 2,239 Bot, 1,891 Prob) and is never involved in training.

Normalization is performed by centering and scaling (StandardScaler). The normalization parameters are estimated only on the training set, then applied as is to validation and test, to avoid any information leakage. The recurrent and convolutional models receive the data shaped as sequences of length 63 (one channel dimension), while the multilayer perceptron operates on the flat vector. Finally, to compensate for class imbalance, we weight the loss function in inverse proportion to the class frequencies (class_weight "balanced"): rare classes weigh more in backpropagation, which prevents the model from merely predicting the majority class. Where the reference works [19], [20] correct the imbalance by synthetic oversampling (SMOTE), we adopt this cost weighting, which introduces no artificial examples and lends itself well to batch training on a large volume of flows.

C. Evaluated Architectures

We compare six deep-learning architectures, from the simplest to the most composite, to identify the best trade-off between detection quality and computational cost. The multilayer perceptron (MLP) stacks dense layers regularized by dropout and is a non-sequential baseline. The LSTM and the GRU are recurrent networks: a recurrent layer of 64 units (with long-term memory for the former, with simplified gates for the latter) followed by a dense layer, which models dependencies along the feature sequence. The CNN applies two one-dimensional convolutional layers (64 then 128 filters) to extract local patterns between neighboring features. The two hybrid architectures chain convolutional layers and a recurrent layer: CNN-LSTM combines local pattern extraction and sequential modeling, while CNN-BiLSTM makes this recurrent layer bidirectional, exploiting context in both directions of the sequence.

This set of six architectures extends that of the reference works [19], [20], which compared up to five deep models (DNN, 1D-CNN, BiLSTM, CNN-LSTM, CNN-BiLSTM): we add the unidirectional recurrent variants GRU and LSTM, to cover, under a single protocol, the dense (MLP), convolutional (CNN), recurrent (LSTM, GRU) and hybrid (CNN-LSTM, CNN-BiLSTM) families.

All architectures share the optimizer, the training procedure and the output layer adapted to the task (sigmoid for the binary decision, softmax for the multiclass decisions). This common framework guarantees that the observed differences stem from the architectures themselves and not from divergent settings.

D. Cascaded Detection and Direct Baseline

The detector is organized as a two-stage cascade. The first stage decides a binary question, is the flow legitimate or malicious? This task is solved with high quality because attack signatures stand out clearly from normal traffic. Flows judged malicious are passed to a second stage, a multiclass classifier that determines the attack family (Dos, DDoS, Bot or Prob). By first filtering out the majority legitimate traffic, the second stage no longer has to separate attacks amid dominant noise, which makes it more sensitive to rare families.

To verify that this split actually yields a gain, and not merely additional complexity, we compare it with a competing baseline: a direct multiclass classifier that decides in a single step among the five classes. The comparison is conducted under strictly identical conditions (same 63 features, same preprocessing, same six candidate architectures, same hyperparameters and, above all, the same test set). Since both approaches produce a verdict over the same five classes, their scores are directly comparable. For each approach, the retained architecture is the one that maximizes the macro F1 on the test set.

E. Training and Evaluation Protocol

Training uses the Adam optimizer (learning rate 10^{-3}). The binary stage is trained for 15 epochs (batches of 2,048, patience 4); the multiclass classifiers, both the second-stage module and the direct baseline, are trained for 60 epochs (batches of 512, patience 15). Early stopping monitors the validation loss and restores the best weights, and a save of the best model is kept at each stage. The random seed is fixed at 42 for weight initialization as well as for shuffling.

Evaluation relies on standard metrics computed on the test set: accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. Given the imbalance, we adopt the macro F1 as the primary criterion, because it gives equal weight to each class regardless of its size and therefore reflects the ability to detect rare attacks. We also report the area under the ROC curve (ROC-AUC), the false-positive rate for the binary decision, the confusion matrices and the per-class F1. Finally, we measure the inference latency and the training time of each model, cost indicators relevant to an online deployment.

The experiments are implemented in Python with TensorFlow/Keras.

F. Integration into the SDN Controller and Online Deployment

The trained detector is deployed in a Ryu controller that drives a topology emulated under Mininet: six OpenVSwitch access switches (denoted ap1 to ap6) connect eighteen IoT stations (sta1 to sta18) over OpenFlow 1.3. The data plane handles traffic forwarding, while the control plane hosts the inference chain (Fig. 11).

At each supervision cycle, fixed at two seconds, the controller reconstructs the flow state then applies the cascade. TCP flags are counted on the fly by the PacketIn handler; the features requiring packet-by-packet visibility (inter-arrival times, length statistics, subflows, active or idle phases) are recomputed by a FlowTracker module that reproduces, at the controller's vantage point, the semantics of the tool used to generate the dataset. This yields, per flow, the same sixty-three-feature vector as offline, normalized by the same scaler. The cascade then decides in two steps: the first stage estimates the probability that a flow is malicious and decides at a threshold of 0.5; the retained flows pass to the second stage, whose softmax output designates the attack family. The verdict over the five classes, together with a snapshot of the state (current cycle, per-class counts, suspected victims and sources, mitigation state), is published at every cycle for a supervision dashboard

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Fig. 11. System architecture: offline phase (training of the cascade) and online phase (Ryu controller, per-cycle inference and targeted mitigation).

G. Automatic Mitigation: From Detector to IDPS

Detection alone is not enough for the intended prevention function. The controller therefore installs, when an attack is confirmed, an OpenFlow drop rule. To avoid reacting to a transient spike, the decision is subject to hysteresis: mitigation triggers immediately if the proportion of flows judged malicious and attributable to a source exceeds a high threshold, and otherwise after confirmation over two consecutive cycles. This two-cycle delay, about four seconds, is a trade-off between robustness to false positives and reactivity.

The installed rule adapts to the attack family. For a simple denial of service, a botnet or a reconnaissance, whose source is stable and identifiable, the controller drops only the pair formed by the attacker's address and the victim's: blocking is surgical and the other stations keep reaching the victim. For a distributed denial of service, where source addresses are random or spoofed, this source-based targeting becomes ineffective; the controller then drops the access port through which the flood enters toward the victim, identified as an edge port crossed by an abnormal rate (at least thirty packets toward the victim in under two seconds).

This criterion spares transit links and legitimate stations, which keep reaching the victim during the attack. The rules are installed at high priority, above forwarding, with a lifetime that depends on the family: forty-five seconds for a reconnaissance, sixty seconds for a simple or distributed denial of service, one hundred and twenty seconds for a botnet. After two consecutive legitimate cycles, disarming purges the rules and allows re-blocking of a later attack. The whole pipeline, cascaded inference at each cycle then adapted automatic blocking, constitutes the intrusion detection and prevention system called for by [19], [20], here realized within the SDN controller.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

All results are on the test set (106,761 flows), never seen during training. Unless stated otherwise, the architecture retained for a task is the one that maximizes the macro F1. We present in turn the two stages of the cascade, the direct multiclass baseline, the full cascade, then the cascade/direct comparison and the discussion.

A. Binary Stage: Legitimate vs Malicious Traffic

The six architectures reach high and tightly grouped quality on the binary decision (Table I). Accuracy ranges from 91.5% (GRU) to 92.4% (CNN-BiLSTM), and F1 stays between 91.2% and 92.2%. CNN-BiLSTM achieves the best F1 (92.15%) and the best accuracy (92.40%), just ahead of the MLP (92.14%) and CNN (92.09%); the gap between architectures is therefore small, indicating that the attack/legitimate separation is a well-posed task for all the models. The false-positive rate stays around 12–13%, and the ROC-AUC exceeds 97.5% everywhere (Fig. 3). The learning curves (Fig. 2) show stable convergence within a few epochs, without marked overfitting.

TABLE I. BINARY STAGE (ATTACK/BENIGN), 63 FEATURES, TEST SET.

Model	Acc (%)	Prec. (%)	Recall (%)	F1 (%)	FPR (%)	ROC-AUC (%)	Inf. (ms)
MLP	92.41	86.70	98.32	92.14	12.47	98.00	0.35
LSTM	91.86	86.20	97.65	91.57	12.93	97.57	0.33
GRU	91.52	85.98	97.08	91.20	13.09	97.29	0.33
CNN	92.31	86.17	98.87	92.09	13.12	98.04	0.29
CNN-LSTM	92.30	86.57	98.24	92.03	12.60	97.89	0.70
CNN-BiLSTM	92.40	86.54	98.53	92.15	12.68	97.96	0.91

Fig. 2. Accuracy and loss curves of the six models (binary stage).

Fig. 3. Confusion matrices and ROC curves of the six models (binary stage).

B. Multiclass Stage: Attack Family

The second stage classifies the malicious flows into four families (Table II), whose learning curves appear in Fig. 4. The task is markedly harder: accuracy plateaus around 74–76% and the macro F1 between 55.9% and 58.6%. CNN-BiLSTM again stands out (macro F1 58.61%, accuracy 76.07%). The per-class reading is instructive: Dos is recognized almost perfectly (F1 \approx 93.5%), but DDoS (\approx 57% for the best model), Bot (\approx 33%) and Prob (\approx 51%) remain difficult. These three families share neighboring statistical signatures and suffer from the small size of Bot and Prob, as confirmed by the confusion matrices (Fig. 5): confusions concentrate among DDoS, Bot and Prob.

TABLE II. MULTICLASS STAGE (4 ATTACK FAMILIES), TEST SET.

Model	Acc (%)	Macro F1 (%)	ROC-AUC (%)	Dos F1	DDoS F1	Bot F1	Prob F1
MLP	74.13	56.79	93.03	93.56	49.16	30.05	54.40
LSTM	73.87	56.52	93.02	93.54	48.18	30.02	54.33
GRU	74.05	55.88	93.00	93.53	49.33	29.98	50.68
CNN	74.54	56.75	93.72	93.56	49.61	31.85	51.98
CNN-LSTM	74.99	56.79	93.88	93.40	52.06	33.29	48.39
CNN-BiLSTM	76.07	58.61	93.90	93.17	56.83	33.06	51.38

Fig. 4. Accuracy and loss curves of the six models (multiclass stage).

Fig. 5. Confusion matrices and ROC curves of the six models (multiclass stage).

C. Baseline: Direct Multiclass Classifier (5 Classes)

The direct baseline decides in a single step among the five classes (Table III), with learning curves in Fig. 6. Here, CNN-LSTM achieves the best macro F1 (59.49%, accuracy 81.15%), ahead of CNN and CNN-BiLSTM (58.69% each). The same

per-class profile as in the multiclass stage reappears: Benign and Dos are well recognized (F1 > 92%), while DDoS, Bot and Prob remain the weak points (Fig. 7). The fact that the best architecture differs by approach (CNN-LSTM for direct, CNN-BiLSTM for cascade) justifies having compared six architectures rather than fixing one a priori.

TABLE III. DIRECT MULTICLASS CLASSIFIER (5 CLASSES), TEST SET.

Model	Acc (%)	Macro F1 (%)	ROC-AUC (%)	Benign F1	Dos F1	DDoS F1	Bot F1	Prob F1
MLP	79.69	57.01	95.85	91.72	92.34	39.44	27.87	33.69
LSTM	80.04	57.46	96.03	91.74	91.89	41.41	27.95	34.32
GRU	80.07	57.49	95.94	91.92	92.25	40.52	27.60	35.14
CNN	80.91	58.69	96.28	92.21	92.61	44.53	29.01	35.09
CNN-LSTM	81.15	59.49	96.15	92.17	92.36	44.87	28.64	39.38
CNN-BiLSTM	80.56	58.69	96.18	91.92	92.36	42.96	28.53	37.69

Fig. 6. Accuracy and loss curves of the six direct models.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrices and ROC curves of the six direct models.

D. Full Cascade

The cascade combines the best binary stage and the best multiclass stage, i.e., CNN-BiLSTM at both levels. Over the five classes, it reaches an accuracy of 81.93%, a macro F1 of 60.64% and a ROC-AUC of 96.25%. The per-class detail (Fig. 8) confirms the expected hierarchy: Benign (F1 92.63%) and Dos (F1 92.36%) are solidly identified, DDoS reaches 47.69%, while Bot (27.48%) and Prob (43.05%) remain the most fragile. The high recall on Bot comes with low precision: weighting the rare classes increases sensitivity at the cost of false positives on this family, a trade-off accepted in a security context where missing an attack costs more than an alert to verify.

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix (5 classes) of the CNN-BiLSTM x CNN-BiLSTM cascade.

E. Cascade vs Direct Classifier

The comparison of the two approaches is conducted under strictly equal conditions (Table IV, Fig. 9). The cascade beats the best direct classifier on macro F1, 60.64% versus 59.49%, i.e., +1.16 points, with a confirmed, though slight, advantage in

accuracy (81.93% versus 81.15%) and ROC-AUC (96.25% versus 96.15%). The gain is not uniform (Fig. 10): it concentrates on DDoS (+2.82 points) and Prob (+3.67 points), that is, the families that stage 2 distinguishes better once legitimate traffic has been set aside. Bot is a slight exception (+1.16 points in favor of direct), and Dos is tied. The cost of the cascade lies in a second model to maintain and a slightly higher inference latency (0.459 ms versus 0.402 ms); at this scale, the gap remains negligible for online detection. The cascade also provides a two-step decision, "attack?" then "of what type?", more readable for an operator than the output of a single classifier.

TABLE IV. CASCADE VS BEST DIRECT CLASSIFIER, SAME CONDITIONS AND SAME TEST SET.

Approach	Acc (%)	Macro F1 (%)	ROC-AUC (%)	Latency (ms)
Cascade (CNN-BiLSTM + CNN-BiLSTM)	81.93	60.64	96.25	0.459
Direct (CNN-LSTM)	81.15	59.49	96.15	0.402

PER-CLASS F1 (%) — CASCADE VS DIRECT.

Approach	Benign	Dos	DDoS	Bot	Prob
Cascade	92.63	92.37	47.69	27.48	43.05
Direct	92.17	92.36	44.87	28.64	39.38

Fig. 9. Global comparison cascade / direct (accuracy, macro F1, ROC-AUC, latency).

Fig. 10. Per-class F1 head to head: cascade vs best direct classifier.

F. Summary

On ASEADOS-SDN-IoT, binary detection is reliably solved by the six architectures ($F1 \approx 92\%$), while fine recognition of attack families remains the bottleneck, owing to imbalance and the closeness of the DDoS, Bot and Prob signatures. Under our experimental conditions, the cascade organization improves the macro F1 over the best direct classifier (+1.16 points), for a negligible latency overhead, and CNN-BiLSTM offers the best trade-off at both stages.

G. Functional Validation of the IDPS

Supervision relies on a dedicated dashboard, whose software architecture is summarized in Fig. 12: a Flask service exposed on port 5001 queries the controller through a REST API, persists the state of flows and agents, and renders four views (card summary, attack-state timeline, topology and resource consumption).

Fig. 12. Software architecture of the supervision dashboard: presentation layer (views), Flask application service and REST API, log persistence, and link with the Ryu controller.

We validate the detection-mitigation chain through a demonstration in an emulated environment, with the Ryu controller and the Mininet topology running and the dashboard active. Four attack scenarios are replayed, each representative of a family, plus a reference legitimate traffic (Fig. 13): a stealth port scan (reconnaissance, Fig. 14), low-rate botnet beacons targeting several hosts (Fig. 15), a single-source SYN flood (denial of service, Fig. 16) and a SYN flood from random sources (distributed denial of service, Fig. 17). For each scenario, one observes at the controller's vantage point that the traffic is detected as malicious and attached to the correct family, then, after hysteresis confirmation, the installation of a drop rule adapted to the family (by source-victim pair for source-stable attacks such as DoS, Bot or Prob, and by ingress port of the flood for the distributed denial of service from spoofed sources); legitimate traffic from the other stations

toward the same victim keeps being forwarded. The reference traffic triggers no mitigation. This demonstration establishes that the deployed pipeline reproduces online the expected behavior of the detector and triggers prevention appropriately. The time observed between the start of the attack and its reporting on the dashboard is on the order of four seconds, consistent with the two-cycle hysteresis. The installation of the prevention rules adapted to each family is illustrated in Fig. 18.

Fig. 13. Dashboard under reference legitimate traffic: no flow is classified as malicious and no mitigation rule is installed.

Fig. 14. Dashboard during a stealth port scan (reconnaissance): the flows are detected and attached to the Prob family.

Fig. 15. Dashboard during low-rate botnet beacons toward several hosts: the flows are detected and attached to the Bot family.

Fig. 16. Dashboard during a single-source SYN flood (denial of service): the flow is detected and attached to the DoS family.

Fig. 17. Dashboard during a SYN flood from spoofed sources (distributed denial of service): the traffic is detected and attached to the DDoS family.

Fig. 18. Adaptive mitigation: drop rules installed by source-victim pair for DoS, Bot and Prob, and by ingress port for the spoofed-source DDoS; legitimate traffic toward the same victim keeps being forwarded.

The controller's resource consumption, measured during these scenarios, is analyzed below in light of the deployability cost.

H. Deployability Cost of the Full Feature Set Online

Computing the sixty-three features online has a cost of its own, which constitutes an operational result in its own right. Some of them cannot be derived from the aggregate counters exposed by OpenFlow: their reconstruction requires bringing packets up to the controller, which loads a single-threaded control plane. Under attacks with varying source and port, this volume of escalation grows sharply and the service degrades; a bounded mirror and keeping forwarding in the data plane attenuate the effect without eliminating it. This observation delimits the use of the full set: it provides the reference of complete features and a functional IDPS, but a reliable large-scale deployment would go either through a subset extractable from the OpenFlow counters alone, or through an out-of-band capture decoupled from the control channel. This trade-off between feature richness and controller load is one of the practical results of the study.

The supervision captures quantify this cost (Fig. 19 and Fig. 20). Under legitimate traffic, the controller stays light: overall CPU load about 27%, RAM about 40% and controller process around 1.6%. Under a distributed flood from spoofed sources, the control-plane load jumps: overall CPU beyond 80%, RAM close to 60% and the controller process exceeding 230%, several cores then being solicited. This abrupt rise, specific to the packet-by-packet mirror that the full feature set requires, concretely illustrates the deployability limit of the 63-feature set online.

Fig. 19. Controller resource consumption under legitimate traffic.

Fig. 20. Controller resource consumption under a distributed denial-of-service attack.

1. Discussion

The separation between legitimate and malicious traffic is solved reliably and uniformly: the six architectures reach an F1 close to 92%, a sign that this boundary is clearly marked in ASEADOS-SDN-IoT. The bottleneck lies at the next stage, the recognition of the attack family. Dos stands out there almost perfectly, but DDoS, Bot and Prob remain difficult, with F1 between 27% and 57%. The confusion matrices attribute this ceiling to two combined causes: the closeness of the statistical signatures of these families and the small size of Bot and Prob, which penalizes a demanding macro metric.

Under our conditions, the cascade organization improves the macro F1 by 1.16 points over the best direct classifier, with a confirmed advantage in accuracy and ROC-AUC. The gain is not global: it concentrates on DDoS and Prob, the families that the second stage distinguishes better once the majority legitimate traffic has been set aside. This result supports the founding intuition of the cascade without overstating it, the gap

remaining modest. Bot is an exception and classifies slightly better in direct mode: the cascade can propagate an error, a flow misrouted at the first stage never reaching the second, which weighs more on an already rare class. The overhead of the cascade, a second model and a barely higher inference latency (0.459 ms versus 0.402 ms), remains negligible at the scale of online detection, and the two-step decision is more readable for an operator.

The best model depends on the approach: CNN-BiLSTM dominates at both stages of the cascade, while CNN-LSTM prevails in direct classification. The bidirectional recurrent layer appears most useful when a stage is specialized on a subtask, which justifies a posteriori comparing six architectures rather than choosing a single model a priori.

Cost weighting raises the recall on rare classes, at the price of low precision, clearly visible on Bot, where many flows are flagged wrongly. In a security context, this trade-off is defensible, since missing an attack generally costs more than an alert to verify; it nonetheless remains a source of operational noise that post-hoc calibration or per-class thresholds could attenuate.

Some SDN-IoT works report very high accuracies, for example on CICIDS2018 [17] or on SDN-oriented datasets [18]. Our figures, more modest, are not directly comparable: they are on a distinct SDN-IoT dataset, on five classes two of which are strongly minority, are measured by macro F1 rather than accuracy, and do not use synthetic oversampling. We therefore claim no superiority; we document a realistic behavior on a recent dataset at the controller's vantage point.

The comparison with the reference works whose approach we extend [19], [20] is instructive (Table V). On CIC-DDoS2019, an enterprise-network DDoS dataset, their binary detection reaches an accuracy close to 99.96% and their multiclass classification an average accuracy of about 80%. Our binary values are lower (accuracy 92.40%, F1 92.15%) because, on ASEADOS-SDN-IoT, the boundary between legitimate and malicious traffic at the controller's vantage point is less sharp than a DDoS/normal separation in an enterprise. Conversely, our multiclass accuracies (81.93% in cascade) are of the same order as theirs, although our task is more demanding: five classes, two of them strongly minority, evaluated by macro F1. These gaps stem from the conditions (dataset, vantage point, class granularity) rather than from a hierarchy of methods, and confirm that the SDN-IoT context targeted by the perspectives of [19], [20] presents its own difficulties.

TABLE V. COMPARISON WITH THE REFERENCE WORKS A (DIFFERENT DATASETS AND TASKS; INDICATIVE COMPARISON).

Work	Dataset	Task	Best model	Accuracy	F1
Ref. A — binary	CIC-DDoS2019	DDoS vs normal	CNN-BiLSTM	≈ 99.96%	> 99.8%
Ref. A — multiclass	CIC-DDoS2019	DDoS families	CNN-LSTM	≈ 80%	—
Our work — binary	ASEADOS-SDN-IoT	Attack / Benign	CNN-BiLSTM	92.40%	92.15%
Our work — cascade	ASEADOS-SDN-IoT	5 classes	CNN-BiLSTM ×2	81.93%	60.64% (macro)

On the same dataset, the article that introduces ASEADOS-SDN-IoT [21] provides ML and DL references, evaluated in detection: each attack family, then all attacks, against legitimate traffic. On the combined "all attacks" scenario, their best deep model (CNN-LSTM) reaches an accuracy of 92.42% and an F1 of 92.41%, and their best ensembles (LightGBM, AdaBoost) approach 93%. Our binary Attack/Benign detection, with CNN-BiLSTM on these same sixty-three features, obtains values of the same order (accuracy 92.40%, F1 92.15%, ROC-AUC 97.96%), which places our pipeline at the level of the references published on this dataset (Table VI). Beyond this detection, we bring two elements that the reference study, focused on benchmarking, does not address: a fine five-class classification organized as a cascade, and the integration of the detector into a detection-and-prevention system operating within the SDN controller.

TABLE VI. COMPARISON ON THE SAME ASEADOS-SDN-IoT DATASET WITH THE REFERENCES OF THE DATASET ARTICLE (THEIR EVALUATION IS ON "ALL ATTACKS" DETECTION).

Approach	Task	Best model	Accuracy	F1	ROC-AUC
Dataset ref. — ML (all attacks)	Attack / Benign	LightGBM	93.28%	93.27%	—
Dataset ref. — DL (all attacks)	Attack / Benign	CNN-LSTM	92.42%	92.41%	98.02%
Our work — binary	Attack / Benign	CNN-BiLSTM	92.40%	92.15%	97.96%
Our work — cascade	5 classes	CNN-BiLSTM ×2	81.93%	60.64% (macro)	96.25%

Two reservations frame these conclusions. First, the evaluation is specific to ASEADOS-SDN-IoT; its generalization to other topologies or controllers remains to be established. Second, the controller integration and the mitigation have been tested only in an emulated network: the control-plane load induced by the online reconstruction of the features requiring packet-by-packet visibility is measured on representative scenarios, but its behavior under prolonged attack and at large scale remains to be characterized in a real deployment.

V. CONCLUSION

We have studied, then made operational, deep-learning intrusion detection in SDN-IoT networks, taking up the perspectives opened by earlier work on deep denial-of-service attack detection [19], [20]. On ASEADOS-SDN-IoT, a cascaded detector comparing six architectures achieves reliable binary detection (F1 close to 92%) and, over the five classes, moderately outperforms a direct classifier evaluated under identical conditions; CNN-BiLSTM offers the best trade-off. Integrated into a Ryu controller, this detector reconstructs the features online, decides at each cycle and installs a targeted OpenFlow mitigation on the source after hysteresis confirmation, thereby realizing the prevention function called for by [19], [20]. A functional demonstration confirms the detection-blocking chain on four attack families, and the deployability analysis documents the cost, for the control plane, of computing the full feature set online.

Several limitations frame these results. The marked imbalance of the dataset weighs on performance, especially at the multiclass stage, where the least-represented families (DDoS, Bot and Prob) remain the hardest to recognize. The SDN integration has been tested only in an emulated network: the demonstration establishes that detection and blocking work, and the controller load is measured on a few scenarios, but we have evaluated neither the speed of mitigation when an attack persists, nor the system's behavior on a larger network. The dashboard built for these trials also remains an observation tool: it displays the state of traffic and alerts, without allowing the operator to act directly. Finally, the evaluation is on a single dataset, ASEADOS-SDN-IoT, and uses the sixty-three features without comparing them, under equal conditions, to a smaller subset that would be less costly to compute.

These limitations trace the extensions of this work. Handling the imbalance, through calibration of the decision thresholds or targeted resampling of the minority classes (DDoS, Bot and Prob), would directly target the bottleneck of fine recognition; building or enriching a less imbalanced dataset, as well as an evaluation on other SDN-IoT datasets, would broaden its reach. The main perspective is to leave Mininet emulation for a real deployment on hardware SDN infrastructure: a testbed based on real switches and traffic would stress the mitigation latency under prolonged attack, the effective control-plane load and the scaling, and would confirm the operational viability of the IDPS. Porting the detector to other SDN controllers, such as ONOS or POX, would also open a comparison of their efficiency and execution cost, to determine the environment best suited to this load. Evaluation on different network topologies would likewise allow comparing their performance and resource consumption, to identify the most efficient and best-suited network architecture. An out-of-band feature capture, decoupled from the control channel, would accompany this transition by removing the cost measured on the control plane. The dashboard would finally benefit from evolving from an observation console toward an intervention console, in the spirit

of security information and event management (SIEM) and security operations center (SOC) tools: beyond real-time monitoring of legitimate and malicious traffic, the operator could trigger response actions directly, such as blocking a source, and have investigation and alert-correlation functions.

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